

ALUMINIUM CHLORIDE AS A CONDENSING AGENT FOR THE PECHMANN REACTION

BY V. M. DIXIT AND A. M. KANAKUDATI

Acetone dicarboxylic acid has been condensed with (i) *meta*-cresol and (ii) pyrogallol in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride as the condensing agent. In addition to the expected product, viz. the respective coumarin-4-acetic acid, the dilactone of $\beta\beta$ -di-(2:3:4-trihydroxyphenyl)glutaric acid has been obtained from the condensation of pyrogallol.

Continuing our investigation on the use of condensing agents other than sulphuric acid for the Pechmann reaction (cf. Dixit, Kanakudati and Mulay, this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 207) (i) *meta*-cresol and (ii) pyrogallol were condensed with acetone dicarboxylic acid in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, following the same procedure as that used for the condensation of resorcin (*loc. cit.*).

m-Cresol gave a small yield of only one product, viz. 7-methylcoumarin-4-acetic acid (m.p. 190°, decomp.) which was identified by equivalent weight, analysis, mixed melting point with a known specimen prepared by Dey's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1606) and conversion into the known 4:7-dimethylcoumarin (m.p. 130°). In spite of repeated attempts, this condensation did not give any non-acidic product corresponding to the glutarodilactone, obtained from resorcin, but by using phosphoryl chloride as a condensing agent, a non-acidic product has been obtained and its constitution is being studied. A full account of this investigation will appear in a subsequent communication.

Pyrogallol condensed smoothly with acetone dicarboxylic acid in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The condensation product was found to contain (i) an acid and (ii) a non-acidic substance. The acid was crystallised from hot water as small hard needles (m.p. 218°, decomp.). It was identified with a known sample of 7:8-dihydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid (II), prepared in accordance with Dey's method (*loc. cit.*) by (i) mixed melting point, (ii) equivalent weight and (iii) conversion into the known ethyl ester (m.p. 196°) and 7:8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (4-methyldaphnetin, m.p. 248°).

This acid was subjected to simultaneous hydrolysis and methylation according to the method of Robertson and Canter (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1875), since on reference to literature it was found that the expected β -2:3:4-trimethoxyphenylglutaconic acid (III) had not been prepared so far. The glutaconic acid was obtained in good yields and its identity was established by equivalent weight, analysis and conversion into its titratable anhydride, semianilide and anil.

The non-acidic condensation product crystallised from hot water in white prismatic plates (m.p. 278-80°) and gave a dark green coloration with ferric chloride in acetone solution. On boiling with a dilute solution of sodium hydroxide it decomposed to pyrogallol. An approximate determination of its molecular weight suggested a condensation of two molecules of pyrogallol with one of acetone dicarboxylic acid. Hence, by analogy with resorcin a constitution of the dilactone (I) of $\beta\beta$ -di-(2:3:4-

trihydroxyphenyl) glutaric acid is proposed for the non-acidic product and the reaction is supposed to take place as under:

As in the case of resorcin, the intermediate glutaric acid (IV) could not be isolated.

On heating the non-acidic compound (I) with 80% sulphuric acid under the usual experimental conditions, the expected 7:8-dihydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid (m.p. 216° , decomp.) was obtained in almost theoretical yield. After removal of the acid, the filtrate was found to contain pyrogallol.

The non-acidic compound (I) was converted into its tetra-acetyl derivative by the action of acetyl chloride, and into its benzoyl derivative by the action of benzoyl chloride in the presence of pyridine.

EXPERIMENTAL

7-Methylcoumarin-4-acetic Acid.—A mixture of acetone dicarboxylic acid (5.5 g.) and *m*-cresol (3.0 g.) was dissolved in dry carbon disulphide (60 c.c.) and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (9 g.) was added in small quantities with shaking. The mixture was then kept overnight under a guard tube and was refluxed on a water-bath for about 4 hours. The bulk of carbon disulphide was then distilled off and the residue finally dried by exposure. Crushed ice (100 g.) and a small quantity

of concentrated HCl (5 c.c.) were added. The resulting mixture was kept in a refrigerator for about 40 hours and then extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was removed and the ethereal layer was shaken carefully with a strong solution of sodium bicarbonate to dissolve the acidic component. On acidifying the bicarbonate layer a solid separated. This was filtered, washed, dried and crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless long needles, m.p. 190° (decomp.), yield 40%. The melting point was not depressed on mixing it with a known specimen of 7-methylcoumarin-4-acetic acid. (Found: Equiv., 218.7. Calc for $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$: Equiv., 218.0).

By carefully heating at its m.p. in a paraffin bath, the 7-methylcoumarin-4-acetic acid was decarboxylated to the known 4 : 7-dimethylcoumarin. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol as long white needles, m.p. 130°; mixed m.p. with a known specimen of the dimethylcoumarin, 128°.

7 : 8-Dihydroxycoumarin-4-acetic Acid.—Powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (27 g.) was added in small quantities with continuous shaking to a fine suspension of acetone dicarboxylic acid (14.5 g.) and pyrogallol (10 g.) in dry carbon disulphide (100 c.c.). The mixture was kept standing for about an hour. The bulk of the carbon disulphide was distilled off and the residue after drying in a current of hot air was mixed with crushed ice (100 g.) and concentrated HCl (10 c.c.). An ash coloured solid separated which was filtered and dried. This was then treated with a solution of sodium bicarbonate. A part of it remained insoluble and was separated by filtration. This was non-acidic product (B). The acidic product (A) separated as a greyish solid on acidification of the filtrate. It was filtered, washed, dried and crystallised from dilute alcohol in short white needles, m.p. 218° (decomp.). It dissolves in dilute alkali solutions with a red colour and gives an intense green colour with ferric chloride in alcoholic solution.

When mixed with a known specimen of 7 : 8-dihydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid the melting point of the acid (A) was not depressed. (Found: Equiv. 234.7. $C_{11}H_8O_6$ requires equiv., 236).

The acid was carefully decarboxylated by heating at its melting point. The resulting 7 : 8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (4-methylaphnetin) crystallised in colorless long needles from dilute alcohol (m.p. 236°) and was identified with a known specimen of the compound by the usual method. The acid was also converted into its known ethyl ester, m.p. 196°. (Found: C, 59.16; H, 4.47. Calc for $C_{13}H_{12}O_6$: C, 59.09; H, 4.54 per cent).

$\beta\beta$ -Di-(2 : 3 : 4-trihydroxyphenyl)-glutarolactone.—The non-acidic condensation product (B), obtained above, was crystallised from dilute alcohol as thick rhombic prisms, m.p. 278-80°, yield 50%.

The dilactone is soluble in hot water, acetone, ethyl acetate, ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol; sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride; insoluble in petroleum benzene, ether, benzene. It gives a dark green coloration with ferric chloride in acetone solution. (Found: C, 50.16; H, 3.58. $C_{17}H_{12}O_8$ requires C, 50.29; H, 3.487 per cent).

Tetra-acetate of the $\beta\beta$ -(2 : 3 : 4-trihydroxyphenyl)-glutarolactone.—The dilactone (1.5 g.) was refluxed with acetyl chloride (15 c.c.) on a water-bath for six hours. The contents were poured on crushed ice (50 g.) and the mixture stirred vigorously.

A pasty mass separated and was solidified by keeping under water for 24 hours to a white powder. This was filtered, washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and water, dried and crystallised from glacial acetic acid as small prisms, m.p. 268°; yield 1.7 g.

The acetyl derivative is soluble in chloroform, acetone, hot glacial acetic acid; sparingly soluble in benzene and ethyl acetate; insoluble in ether, petroleum benzene, alcohol and water. It did not give any coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 58.08; H, 4.115. $C_{25}H_{20}O_{12}$ requires C, 58.59; H, 3.905 per cent).

Dibenzoate of the $\beta\beta$ -Di-(2:3:4-trihydroxyphenyl)-glutarolactone.—The dilactone (1.0 g.) was dissolved in dry pyridine (10 c.c.) and benzoyl chloride (2.5 g.) was added to the solution in small quantities and with shaking. The mixture was then refluxed on a water-bath for about six hours. Excess of pyridine was removed by slow evaporation and the residue was mixed with ice-cold water (40 c.c.) containing a few c.c. of concentrated HCl when a pink coloured solid separated. This was filtered and washed with dilute alcohol and dried. It crystallised as colorless light plates, m.p. 110°, yield 2.5 g. It is soluble in most of the common organic solvents and gives a greenish coloration with ferric chloride in acetone. (Found: C, 67.51; H, 3.72. $C_{31}H_{20}O_{10}$ requires C, 67.39; H, 3.62 per cent).

Action of 80% Sulphuric Acid on the $\beta\beta$ -Di-(2:3:4-trihydroxyphenyl)-glutarolactone.—The dilactone (2 g.) was dissolved in warm sulphuric acid (25 c.c., 80%) and the mixture was kept standing for 4 hours. It was then poured on ice. After several hours, a white solid separated. This was filtered and the residue was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution, filtered and the filtrate was acidified with HCl. A white crystalline precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed and crystallised from dilute alcohol as short, white needles, m.p. 216°; mixed m.p. with a known specimen of 7:8-dihydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid (Dey, *loc. cit.*), 216°.

The first filtrate mentioned above gave a bluish black coloration with ferric chloride and other characteristic reactions of pyrogallol.

β -2:3:4-Trimethoxyphenylglutaconic Acid.—7:8-Dihydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid (20 g.) was dissolved in an aqueous solution of caustic soda (150 c.c., 30%) and dimethyl sulphate (50 c.c.) was slowly added to the solution with continuous shaking. A further quantity of NaOH solution (25 c.c. of 30%) was added and the contents refluxed on a water-bath for 3 hours.

On cooling, crystals of sodium sulphate separated and were removed by filtration. On acidifying the filtrate a semi-solid mass separated. It was washed and dissolved in a solution of sodium bicarbonate. The solution was shaken with ether to remove non-acidic matter and then acidified with HCl. The white crystalline precipitate thus obtained was filtered, washed and crystallised from dilute acetic acid as stout rhombic crystals, m.p. 167° (decomp.), yield 12.3 g. The equivalent weight agreed with the formula of the glutaconic acid with one molecule of water of crystallisation. (Found: Equiv., 157.3. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{16}O_7$, H_2O : Equiv., 157.0). A dehydrated sample of the acid was used for analysis. (Found: C, 56.66; H, 5.63. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{14}O_7$: C, 56.78; H, 5.456 per cent.)

Derivatives of the β -2 : 3 : 4-Trimethoxyphenylglutaconic Acid: The *anhydride* was prepared by heating the glutaconic acid (2 g.) at 180° and extracting the residue with benzene or glacial acetic acid as prismatic crystals (from glacial acetic acid), m.p. 88° - 90° . It gives a green coloration with ferric chloride in acetone solution. In contact with even a dilute solution of alkali, the anhydride slowly hydrolyses to the original glutaconic acid.

Semianilide was prepared by warming a solution of the anhydride (m.p. 90°) in benzene with a small quantity of aniline for about 15 minutes. Colorless thin plates, m.p. 150 - 52° . (Found: Equiv., 370.8. $C_{20}H_{21}O_6N$ requires equiv., 371.3).

Anil was obtained on heating the anhydrous glutaconic acid (4 g.) with aniline (1.5 g.) at 140° - 160° for two hours. The residue was extracted with glacial acetic acid as small white crystals, m.p. 185° . As expected, the anil is titratable. (Found: Equiv., 351.8; N, 3.87. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4N$ requires equiv., 353.0; N, 3.96 per cent).

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
KARNATAK COLLEGE, DHARWAR.

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